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STRESS IN THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTRUCTORS DURING WARTIME

Abstract.

This article is devoted to the study of stress in the professional activities of instructors in higher medical education institutions during wartime. Military actions create additional psychological pressure on educators, causing high levels of stress and professional burnout. The main stress factors include physical danger, psychological pressure, the need to transition to remote learning, decreased student motivation, and increased workload.

Keywords: *stress, war, professional activities, instructors, higher education institutions, medical education, psychological support, professional burnout, remote learning.*

Introduction

Stress is an integral part of the professional activities of educators in higher medical education institutions, especially during wartime. Military actions significantly affect the psycho-emotional state of teachers, forcing them to adapt to new working conditions. The COVID-19 pandemic has already prepared educators for remote learning, but military actions create new, significantly more complex challenges. This article discusses the main factors of stress in the professional activities of educators during wartime. The aim of this work was to study the stress faced by higher education instructors during military conflicts.

Material and Methods

To achieve the aim, a literature search was conducted in specified databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed Medline, and Embase, as well as from other open sources. The main aspects considered included the impact of military actions on the mental and emotional health of educators, stress reactions and their consequences, as well as effective psychological support and strategies to reduce the impact of stress on professional activities.

Results

Stress, its factors, and consequences among medical education instructors.

Teaching stress is defined as experiencing negative and unpleasant emotions that arise during everyday work [5]. According to research conducted in the USA, educators experience job-related stress twice as often as the general working population [10].

Recent studies have shown that stress levels among medical instructors are extremely high, with the main contributing factors being high performance demands, insufficient administrative support, and challenging working conditions. This highlights the need

for comprehensive support programs for educators to reduce stress levels and improve work efficiency [2].

According to a study conducted at Lahore Medical & Dental College and Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, stress was found in 94% of respondents, with 21% experiencing severe stress. The main stress factors included insufficient control over the work process (96%), difficulty expressing thoughts (70%), unsafe working conditions (66%), work overload and unrealistic deadlines (62%), and work pressure affecting personal life (59%) [6].

Mental and emotional health of ukrainian citizens during wartime. According to the DSM-5, war is considered a significant stressor that meets trauma criteria. Trauma is defined as "actual or threatened death, serious injury, or sexual violence" [1].

Research results indicate that stress during the war in Ukraine is a major and complex issue affecting the mental and emotional health of the country's citizens [8]. The ongoing military conflicts in eastern Ukraine create extreme stress conditions due to the constant threat to life, physical and psychological injuries, fear for the future, evacuations, loss of loved ones, and property destruction. The main stress factors during the war in Ukraine include constant anxiety and fear of enemy attacks, traumatic experiences from military actions, high levels of uncertainty, and future unpredictability. People, especially those living in conflict zones, may suffer from severe psychological problems such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), as well as feelings of social isolation and alienation.

According to WHO estimates, around 22% of people during wartime may experience depressive and anxiety disorders, PTSD, as well as bipolar disorder and schizophrenia in the following years. Depression and

anxiety are correlated with age, with depressive disorders being more frequently diagnosed among women [3,4].

The impact of war on mental health has been observed both among Ukrainian citizens directly affected and among the population living outside the conflict zone [12].

Anxiety-depressive disorders have a profound impact on various aspects of life, including the social sphere, professional activities, and overall quality of life. Studies have shown that a person's psychological state is closely linked to the intensity of social events. In particular, increased stress levels can lead to asthenia, characterized by general weakness and fatigue, as well as increased anxiety and depression. These mental disorders can significantly reduce people's ability to perform their professional duties, maintain social connections, and function in everyday life. Traumatic events often cause deep emotional experiences that affect cognitive processes such as memory, concentration, and decision-making ability. Moreover, they can lead to significant changes in behavior, including avoiding social contacts, reduced activity, and interest in previously significant activities. Changes in emotional state may manifest through feelings of helplessness, irritation, or even aggression, further complicating adaptation to new living conditions [9].

Research shows that during the war in Ukraine, the level of psychological distress can reach 47%, and PTSD is found in about 5% of the population. A link has also been established between the frequency of traumatic events and the increased prevalence of these disorders. For example, in conflict zones like Ukraine, studies have shown a direct link between the impact of war, including combat actions, financial instability, and forced displacement, and the occurrence of psychological disorders and PTSD symptoms among the affected population. Additionally, chronic stress can lead to other health problems, such as an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, sleep disorders, and exacerbation of chronic illnesses. Uncertainty about the future, constant tension, and losses create additional psychological pressure, complicating the adaptation and recovery processes among the population experiencing these tragic events [11].

Stress among Instructors during Wartime.

War creates additional challenges for instructors, including:

- *Physical danger:* Instructors, like the rest of the population, face risks to life and health due to military actions. Destroyed infrastructure and the lack of basic safety conditions make conducting classes difficult or impossible.

- *Psychological pressure:* Feelings of uncertainty, fear for loved ones, and general anxiety create constant mental stress. These factors can lead to chronic anxiety, depression, and other mental disorders.

- *Transition to remote learning:* The need to quickly master new technologies, adapt teaching materials, and ensure effective remote teaching creates additional stress.

- *Decreased student motivation:* Lack of access to resources, students' psychological problems, and general instability can lead to decreased motivation to learn.

- *Increased workload:* The need for constant student support, additional administrative duties, and acting as a psychologist for students add to instructors' workload.

The highest stress levels are found among instructors who have been in the combat zone or nearby since the beginning of the war; the lowest stress levels are found among instructors who have left Ukraine [7].

Conclusions

Stress in the professional activities of medical higher education instructors during wartime is a complex challenge requiring a comprehensive approach to overcome it. Creating a safe educational environment, support from administration, interaction with colleagues, personal responsibility, and the development of professional skills, as well as psychological support from specialists, can significantly reduce the negative impact of stress.

References:

1. American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. 5th ed. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association; 2013.
2. Anil H, Mohan TT, Biju F, Saji S, Gopal RK, Sebastian SR. Epidemiology of workplace stress among medical educators in Pathanamthitta District, Kerala, India. *Prevent Med Res Rev.* 2024;1(2):118-20. doi: 10.4103/PMRR.PMRR_95.
3. Cénat JM, Darius WP, Noorishad P-G, McIntee S-E, Dromer E, Mukunzi JN, et al. War in Ukraine and racism: The physical and mental health of refugees of color matters. *Int J Public Health.* 2022;67:1604990.
4. Charlson F, Ommeren van M, Flaxman A, Cornett J, Whiteford H, Saxena S. New WHO prevalence estimates of mental disorders in conflict settings: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet.* 2019;394(10194):240-248.
5. Collie RJ, Shapka JD, Perry NE. School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy. *J Educ Psychol.* 2012;104(4):1189. doi: 10.1037/a0029356.
6. Daud S, Kashif R, Shuja H. Stress in medical educators. *Prof Med J.* 2012;19(3):404-410.
7. Kipenskyi A, Pidbutska N, Ponomaryov O. Features of overcoming stress during martial law by higher education teachers. *Theory and Practice of Social Systems Management.* 2023;1:65. doi: 10.20998/2078-7782.2023.1.05.
8. Lushchak O, Velykodna M, Bolman S, Strilbytska O, Berezovskyi V, Storey KB. Prevalence of stress, anxiety, and symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder among Ukrainians after the first year of Russian invasion: a nationwide cross-sectional study. *Lancet Reg Health Eur.* 2023 Nov 6;36:100773. doi: 10.1016/j.lanep.2023.100773.
9. Spytska L. Anxiety and depressive personality disorders in the modern world. *Acta Psychol (Amst).* 2024 Jun;246:104285. doi: 10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104285.